

An Analysis of Profitability and Liquidity Position of Tamilnadu based Private Sector Banks

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Abstract

The banking system of India should not only be hassle-free, but it should be able to meet new challenges posed by the technology and any other external and internal factors. Without an effective and sound banking system in India, it is not possible to have a healthy economy.

For the past three decades, India's banking system has several outstanding achievements to its credit. The most striking is the extensive reach. It is no longer confined to only metropolitans or cosmopolitans in India. The Indian banking system has reached even to the remote corners of the country. This is one of the main reasons for India's growth process.

Keywords: Reserve Bank of India, Liquidity, Profitability, Deposits and Loans etc.

History of Banks in India

In India, the ancient Hindu scriptures refer to the money lending activities in the Vedic period. During the Smrity period, which followed the Vedic period, the business of banking was primarily carried on by the members of the Vaish community. The banker in this period performed many of the functions which a modern banker performs these days, namely, accepting deposits, granting advances, acting as banker to the State and issuing and managing the currency of the country.

By 1990s, the market expanded with the establishment of banks such as Punjab National Bank in 1895 in Lahore and Bank of India in 1906 in Mumbai, both of which were founded under private ownership. At the end of the late eighteenth century, there were hardly any banks in India in the modern sense of the term. At the time of the American Civil War, a void was created as the supply of cotton to Lancashire was stopped by the Americans. Some banks were opened at that time, which functioned as entities to finance industry, including speculative trade in cotton. With large exposure to speculative ventures, most of the banks opened in India during that period could not survive and failed. The depositors lost interest and lost money in keeping deposits with banks. Subsequently, banking in India remained the exclusive domain of Europeans for the next several decades until the beginning of the twentieth century.

There was potential for many new banks as the economy was growing. Under such circumstances, many Indians came forward to set up banks, and many banks were set up at that time. A number of them have survived to the present, such as Bank of India, Corporation Bank, Bank of Baroda, Canara Bank and Indian Bank.

The period between the Second World War and the First World War were challenging for the Indian Banking. Likewise, the partition of India in 1947 had adversely impacted the economies of Punjab, and West Bengal and banking activities had remained paralyzed for months. India's independence marked the end of the regime of the laissez-faire for Indian banking. The Government of India initiated measures to play an active role in the economic life of the nation and the industrial policy resolution adopted by the Government in 1948 envisaged a mixed economy. This resulted in greater involvement of the State in different segments of the economy, finance and including banking.

Nationalization of Banks

India marched towards the establishment and expansion of Public Sector Banking through the progressive nationalisation of commercial banks. There were three phases of nationalization, namely, nationalization of Imperial Bank of India in 1955 and its seven associate banks in 1959 – 60, nationalization of fourteen major commercial banks in 1969 and nationalization of six more commercial banks in 1980.

On 1st July 1955, the Government of India nationalised converted it into the State Bank of India and the Imperial Bank of India. The establishment of the State Bank of India was a pioneering attempt in introducing public sector banking in the country. Later on, in 1959 – 60, seven subsidiary banks were also nationalized to form the State Bank of India group. The State Bank of India group had its laudable objective of bringing rural orientation in Indian banking, which is achieved with remarkable success.

For a short period from December 1967 to June 1969, the Government of India pursued the policy of social control on banks aiming at an equitable and purposeful distribution of credit towards development needs. However, the Government was not fully satisfied with the implementation of social control over banks in achieving social goals. An idea was mooted that social ownership would serve a better purpose rather than mere social control over banks.

On 15th April 1980, six more Indian scheduled commercial banks with a deposit of over rupees two hundred crores were nationalized. The nationalized banks were the Andhra Bank, the Corporation Bank, the New Bank of India, the Oriental Bank of Commerce, the Punjab and Sind Bank and the Vijaya Bank. Over ninety per cent of banking activity in the country was brought under public control, by the second dose of nationalization. Nationalization of banks was a bold and major step in the process of banking reforms in the country. It has resulted in the evolution of public sector banking. As an impact of nationalization, the structure of Indian commercial banks has radically changed. Apart from the phenomenal growth of banking institutions in the country, Government ownership and control over the banking business also led to dynamic changes in the banking policies and new strategies of banking development during two decades of post nationalization period.

Liberalization of Banks

In the early 1990s, the Central Government, under the Prime Minister, Shri Narasima Rao embarked on a policy of liberalization and gave licenses to a small number of private banks, which came to be known as new generation tech-savvy banks, which included banks such as UTI Bank, now renamed Axis Bank, HDFC Bank and ICICI Bank. This step, along with the rapid growth in

the economy of India kick-started the banking sector in India, which has seen rapid growth with an active contribution from all the three-sector banks, namely, Government Banks, Private Sector Banks and Foreign Banks.

Contribution of Banks to Economic Development

With the increasing maturity of a country's economy, the growth of specialized financial institutions is inevitable for economic development that too in a developing economy like India, which is poised for growth. Many internal problems like poor capital formation, neglect of rural sector, stronghold of the private money lenders in certain spheres of the economy, poor banking habits on the part of the people, low rates of domestic savings, slow industrial development, low standards of living and the problem of unemployment and under employment are rampant in the economy. These problems are to be tackled urgently.

Banking occupies one of the most important positions in the modern economic world. The banks constitute the lifeline of a sound economy. As such, they lubricate and cater to all sorts of economic activities. The functions of banks in advanced economies are so enormous that we cannot imagine a state without banks.

Current Situation

Currently, banking in India is generally mature in terms of supply, product range and reach, even though, reach in rural India remains a challenge for the private sector banks and foreign banks. In terms of quality of assets and capital adequacy, Indian banks are considered to have clean, transparent and robust balance sheets relative to other banks in comparable economies in the region.

With the growth in the Indian economy which is expected to move faster, especially in the services sector, the demand for the banking services, especially retail banking, mortgages and investment services are expected to be strong. Mergers and acquisitions, takeovers and asset sales are expected to increase.

In recent years, commercial banks in India have been adopting the strategy of innovative banking in their business operations. Innovative banking implies the application of new techniques, new methods and novel schemes in the area of deposit deployment, bank management and mobilization of credit. To attract more deposits, Indian banks have introduced many attractive systems such as education deposit plan, premium pension plan, reinvestment schemes, loan linked recurring deposit plan and the like. Several banks have started evening branches, Sunday branches and round the clock exchange bureau for the benefit of their customers. Likewise, innovations are made on the credit side also. Banks have introduced education loan scheme, debit and credit card scheme, housing finance, consumers' credit, mutual funds, pension plan and the like. Banking services include Automated Teller Machines, shared ATM networks, electronic funds transfer at point of sales, smart cards, phone banking and intranet internet banking. The salient features of these services are the overwhelming reliance on information technology and the absence of physical bank branches to deliver these services to the customers.

Statement of the Problem

Private sector banks have played a major role in the development of the Indian banking industry. They have made banking more efficient and customer friendly. In the process, they have jolted public sector banks, forced and out of complacency them to become more competitive. A study of the performance of private sector banks has assumed significance in this regard. Tamil Nadu, which is one of the first states in the country in terms of overall development, is the fifth-largest

contributor to India's gross domestic product and is the most urbanized State in India. Compared to its share of the population, Tamil Nadu has the highest number of business enterprises in India.

Hence, the researcher has attempted to study the performance of private sector banks based in Tamil Nadu. The private sector banks based in Tamil Nadu are the City Union Bank Limited, the Karur Vysya Bank Limited, the Lakshmi Vilas Bank Limited and the Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Limited. Hence the researcher has undertaken to analyze the performance of these private sector banks. The researcher has planned to study the performance of banks for over ten years, from 1998 to 2008. The research problem chosen for the present study is "The Performance of Private Sector Banks Based in Tamil Nadu".

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to study the performance of private sector banks based in Tamil Nadu. The specific objectives are:

1. To measure the deposits of selected banks.
2. To examine the advances of selected banks.
3. To highlight the investments of selected banks.
4. To study the level of non-performing assets of selected banks.
5. To analyze the profits of selected banks and
6. To identify the factors that influence the profits of selected banks.

Significance of the Study

"Banking means the accepting for the lending of the deposits of money from the public". The present study is expected to throw light into the accepting of deposit, the pattern of lending, the quantum of investment, the impact of non-performing assets and the profitability of private sector banks. This analysis intends to help the bankers and the planners in the Government to frame suitable policies in this regard to sustain and develop the operations of the banking sector.

Limitations of the Study

The duration of the study is limited to the period between 2008 and 2018. The study is limited to the private sector banks based in Tamil Nadu only. The data collected for the present study is secondary.

Methodology

The researcher has collected secondary data relating to deposits, advances, investments, non-performing assets and profits of the selected banks from 2008-2009 to 2017-2018 for analysis.

Tools of Analysis

The researcher has used the following tools for analyzing the performance of selected banks under study.

Percentage Analysis

To study the changes of various factors, deposits, namely, advances, investments, non-performing assets profits during and the period of study, percentages have been computed, taking the values in the year 2018 as the base. The following formula has been used to find out percentages.

$$\text{Percentage} = (v1/v0) \times 100$$

V1 = Value in the current year

V0 = Value in the base year, namely, 2018

Average

The arithmetic average of the various factors namely, deposits, advances, investments, non-performing assets and profits during the period of study have been computed by using the formula,

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where

X = Average value

$\sum X$ = Sum of the values

N = Total number of years

Co efficient of Variation

To test the consistency of the values of the variables, the coefficient of variation measure has been used. The factor with a low value of co efficient of variation is considered as the value with higher consistency. Co efficient of variation is calculated by using the following formula.

Co efficient of variation = $100\sigma / \bar{X}$

Where \bar{x} = Average value

σ = Standard Deviation of values

σ is calculated by using the formula

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2}{N} - (\bar{X})^2}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2}{N} - (\bar{X})^2}$$

Where

N = Total number of years

$X^2 = (x - \bar{x})^2$

X = the values of the factor

Annual Growth

The average annual growth for the various factors, namely, deposits, advances, investments, non-performing assets and profits during the period of study are computed by averaging the annual increases of values over the years.

Compound Growth Rate

The compound growth rate is used to describe the growth of various factors, namely, deposits, advances, investments, non-performing assets and profits over the period selected for the study. It is the geometric mean growth rate on an annualized basis. The formula used to compute the compound growth rate is given below.

T0

=

Base Year, namely, 2008

T1

=

Year at the end of the period, namely, 2018

V (t0) =

Value at the beginning

V (t1) =

Value at the end of the period

Regression Analysis

The researcher has attempted to analyze the level of influence of independent factors, namely, deposits, advances, investments and non-performing assets on the dependent factor profits of banks selected for the study. The following multiple linear regression model has been used for this purpose.

$$P = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4$$

Where

P = Profits

a = constant value

X₁ = deposits

X₂ = advances

X₃ = investments

X₄ = non-performing assets

b₁ = regression co efficient value of deposits b₂= regression co efficient value of advances

b₃ = regression co efficient value of investments, b₄ = regression co efficient value of non-performing assets.

Findings from the Study

From the analysis found that the Karur Vysya Bank had the highest growth was recorded during the year 2015 at 525.60 %. The present research revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean value of share capital with selected commercial banks in the study period.

It is furnished that share capital of all the Tamilnadu based private sector banks had better position except KVB because of the highest coefficient of variation and banks had raised share capital is less value where as other selected private commercial banks.

Karur Vysya Bank had the highest % of growth recorded during the year 2015 at 96.60%, and the Lakshmi Vilas Bank had the highest growth rate recorded at 58.42% in 2013. However, selected commercial banks had negative growth in reserves and surplus in the study period.

It is revealed that reserves and surplus of all the Tamilnadu based private sector banks had better position except KVB because of the highest coefficient of variation and banks had met heavy competition among the public and selected private commercial banks.

Karur Vysya Bank had the highest % of growth was recorded in Deposits during the year 2011 at 34.36%.

Lakshmi Vilas Bank high the est growth rate was recorded in Deposits at 31.09% in the year 2012. The Researcher furnished that, there is a significant difference in the mean value of deposits between the selected private commercial banks for the duration of the study period.

It is revealed that deposits of all the Tamilnadu based private sector banks had better position except CUB because of the highest coefficient of variation and banks had met heavy competition, interest rates are frequently changed by RBI, high operating expenditure, low rate of interest, only attractive special customers etc.,

The present study revealed that there is a major difference in the mean value in borrowings with selected commercial banks in the study period. It is furnished that borrowings of selected commercial banks had better position except for KVB because of the highest coefficient of variation and banks had borrowed highest rate of interest in this study period where as other selected private commercial banks. However, selected commercial banks had negative growth in other liabilities and provisions in the period of the research study.

Suggestions and Recommendations

Based on the outcomes and end of this study, the following policy implications can be recommended for the bankers and policy makers:

Common Suggestions and Recommendations

The common suggestions that the Indian commercial banks should decide to increase their financial feasibility and get better financial strength.

The monetary background for the banks has been changing, and banks want the flexibility to act in response in this altering place.

Computerization and e-services of banking play a significant role in reducing the operating expenses and raising the profits of the banks. The selected Private sector banks are required to concentrate on digitalization to improve their competence.

In India, many areas are still unbanked. The private sector banks are requested to focus on these areas to add to their business. But at the same time, bank branch feasibility must be ensured.

Now-a- days’ customers expect more and more services ready at hand from the banks. So banks are required to offer consumer-oriented products to attract customers.

All the banks are expanding their business these days. Interest income is not only focused, but also the banks are required to take care of earning non-interest income to increase their earning capability.

In India, some commercial banks are very small in size and paying attention in local areas only. So these banks are forced to change their organizational structure and adopt customer-oriented business models to make sure their good endurance.

Risk management plays an essential role in the well being of commercial banks. The banks have guaranteed to proper risk management against liquidity risk, interest rate risk, credit risk and bankruptcy risk. Also, it helps to sustain development in their business.

Banks need to take care of best practices of corporate power and communal, social responsibility to provide the needs of different stakeholders. Competition ever-increasing day-by-day so, the banks should concentrate on fulfilling the needs of the customers.

Conclusion

Liquidity, Profitability and Solvency are the three essential dimensions which help to not only in evaluating the performance of the banks but also participate a vital role in shaping the monetary capability of the banks. Different banks have different strengths and weakness in these performance dimensions. Changing the ownership with different capital structure, poor ratios like low liquid assets to total assets, liquid assets to demand deposits and demand deposits to total deposits does not mean that banks are under liquidity pressures. Favourable ratios like high very high capital adequacy ratio, debt-equity ratio, costs to income ratio do not always depict the soundness of the bank. The study finds that the liquidity position of Tamilnadu based private sector banks KVB, TMB, CUB and LVB are high as compared to the other commercial banks, but these banks should also take care of their profitability as high liquidity might hurt the long term investment of these banks. These private sector banks are highly profitable banks during the study period. In the end, it is recommended that Tamilnadu based private sector banks are required to maintain sufficient balance between liquidity and profitability to enhance their solvency level.

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